

Raureflexine, an Unusual Bis(indole) Alkaloid from *Rauwolfia reflexa* Teijm and Binn.[†]

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The structure of raureflexine, an unusual and interesting bis-indole alkaloid, isolated from *Rauwolfia reflexa* Teijm and Binn. (Fam. Apocynaceae) has been established as the dimer of its congener, rauflexine, the two monomeric units being bridged by a methylene group.

In continuation of our studies on the chemistry of the alkaloids of *Rauwolfia* species^{1,2}, the basic constituents of *Rauwolfia reflexa* Teijm and Binn. have been reinvestigated. From the leaves of this plant four new indole constituents, rauflexine (1)³, reflexine (2)³, flexicorine (3)⁴ and raureflexine (4) have been isolated.

Flexicorine is a bis-indole alkaloid having an unusual structure with an iminoquinone system. Such an iminoquinone system was hitherto unknown in indole chemistry. The present communication is concerned with the structure elucidation of raureflexine which is also a bis-indole alkaloid closely related to rauflexine³.

The benzene-soluble fraction of the ethanolic extract of the leaves yielded a complex mixture of alkaloids. It could be resolved into pure components on Tswett column over neutral alumina. The eluates from n-hexane and benzene

mixture afforded rauflexine (1)³ and reflexine (2)³. The concentrate of the 5% methanolic-chloroform eluate afforded two compounds. The more polar constituent on preparative thin layer chromatography using methanol afforded flexicorine (3). Raureflexine (4) was isolated as the less polar, minor constituent. The latter produced blue colouration with ceric ammonium sulphate, typical of an indoline chromophore. Thin layer chromatography afforded raureflexine as a white amorphous solid (0.005%), d.p. 216–18°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} +328.2^\circ$. The high resolution mass spectrum exhibited the molecular ion peak M^+ 684.3619 corresponding to the molecular formula $C_{43}H_{48}N_4O_4$. This provided positive evidence regarding the dimeric nature of the alkaloid.

In the ultraviolet spectrum, the absorption maxima was observed at λ_{max} (EtOH) 213 (log ϵ 4.76), 256 (4.19) and

300 nm (4.00), the values being typical of deacetylvindoline⁵ (5). From the ultraviolet spectral data the methoxyindoline functionality could be ascertained⁵. The special features in the infrared spectrum were the presence of an unconjugated carbonyl group, olefinic function and absence of N_aH/N_bH . The high resolution mass spectra showed the molecular ion peak at m/z 684.3698 (M^+) [100%]. This base peak suffered cleavage generating ion fragments as expected at 656, 655, 641, 586, 561, 398, 349, 336, 335, 226, 213, 212, 188, 174 and 159. The fragments m/z 336 and 335 corresponded exactly with those observed in the mass spectrum of rauflexine (1). The high resolution mass spectra revealed

[†]Dedicated to Professor Sukh Dev on the occasion of his 75th. birth anniversary.

that raureflexine is the dimer of rauflexine, the two monomers being linked through a methylene bridge, indicated from the ion peak at m/z 349 which can be accounted for by a second rauflexine unit ($M^+ - 1$) attached to one CH_2 group.

From a careful analysis of the ^1H nmr (400 MHz) spectrum it has been possible to ascertain the functionalities and structural features of the molecule. The ^1H nmr spectra showed four aromatic protons as singlets (2H each) at δ 7.03 and 6.28, one olefinic proton (quartet) at δ 5.33 and the vinylic methyl as a doublet at δ 1.60 (J 6.0 Hz). Two indoline- N - CH_3 groups resonated at δ 2.78. The chemical shifts for the two aromatic methoxys appeared at δ 3.84, two benzylic protons at δ 3.54 (br). The ^1H nmr spectra of raureflexine (4) and rauflexine (1)³ were almost identical except at C_{10} in the aromatic ring, the C_{10} proton being absent in the former. This indicated that in raureflexine the two monomers are linked through a methylene bridge at C_{10} - C_{10}' .

From the studies of the ^{13}C nmr spectra (including coupled and APT spectra) it was evident that the twenty carbon signals of raureflexine (4) showed striking resemblance to that of rauflexine (1). A comparison of the spectra of 1 and 4 has been presented in Table 1.

TABLE 1—CARBON CHEMICAL SHIFT (PPM) OF RAUFLEXINE AND RAUREFLEXINE

Carbon	Rauflexine	Raureflexine	Multiplicity
2	78.4	78.6	d
3	50.1	50.2	d
5	53.1	53.3	d
6	31.5	29.7	t
7	57.8	58.1	s
8	124.6	124.5	s
9	121.5	121.3	d
10	103.8	—	d
10	—	116.3	s
11	160.4	158.0	s
12	97.5	94.7	d
13	155.1	153.3	s
14	35.3	34.9	t
15	28.5	28.5	d
16	50.3	50.2	d
17	214.2	212.1	s
18	12.9	12.9	q
19	120.2	121.2	d
20	137.3	136.9	s
21	55.7	55.6	t
- NCH_3	34.2	34.7	q
- Ar-O-CH_3	55.3	55.5	q
Ar-CH_2 - Ar	—	32.9	t

Experimental

M.p.s. were recorded in a Kofler block apparatus and are uncorrected. Uv spectra (in 95% aldehyde free ethanol) were recorded in a Varian Techtron 634 spectrophotometer, ir spectra (KBr) in a Perkin-Elmer 782 spectrophotometer, and ^1H nmr (400 MHz) and ^{13}C nmr (50 MHz) spectra (CDCl_3) on Varian XL-400 and XL-200 spectrometers. The rotation was determined in spectral chloroform at room temperature on a Perkin-Elmer 241 polarimeter. Column chromatography was carried out with Brockmann alumina and thin layer chromatographic experiments were carried out with silica gel (Merck) plates.

Air-dried and milled leaves (2 kg) of *R. reflexa* Teijm and Binn. were extracted with ethanol (5.0 dm^3) for 30 days at 26° and filtered. The ethanolic extract was concentrated under reduced pressure and churned with 5% aqueous citric acid (1.5 dm^3) for 12 h. The resulting mixture was filtered through a bed of celite. The aqueous filtrate was completely basified with liquor ammonia and the precipitated base was extracted successively with benzene ($3 \times 1.5 \text{ dm}^3$). The organic layer was made ammonia-free by repeated washing with water and dried. The benzene concentrate was chromatographed over alumina. The 5% methanolic chloroform eluate afforded a deep brown gum. The major component of the gum on preparative tlc ($R_f = 0.42$, silica gel, MeOH) afforded flexicorine. The minor component ($R_f = 0.26$, silica gel, MeOH) on elution with 10% MeOH- CHCl_3 afforded raureflexine (0.005%), d.p. 217 – 18° , $[\alpha]_D^{25} +328.2^\circ$ ($c = 1.03$, CHCl_3) (rose-red colour with conc. HNO_3 ; dirty yellow colour with conc. H_2SO_4 ; blue colour with ceric ammonium sulphate).

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